

Results in Brief, portraits of project innovations

Wood Pulp Panels

fibre panels for thermal building insulation

Wood Pulp Panels are glue free wood fibre panels for thermal building insulation. Applicable in roof or wall insulations they are a biobased alternative to most current insulation materials and breaking ground for closed loop circular value chain applications.

APPLICATION

Modern wooden houses convince with high living comfort, extremely short construction times through off-site prefabrication, and **low environmental impact** of the natural building materials. This better performance compared to conventional non-biobased materials can still be improved by reducing the little amounts

of fossil-based components such as plastic fibres or fossil-based binders. BASAJAUN Wood Pulp Panels (WPP) for thermal building insulation developed by VTT in Finland address this challenge by using paper pulp (CTMP) in a **foam forming process**. For the final panel, no glue is necessary to reach comparable properties as other insulation materials.

It can be integrated into the prefabrication process in wood construction and be applied in conventional buildings as thermal wall and roof insulation material. Being highly biobased it is designed for further **use in closed circular economy material loops** at the end of the building use cycle. Post treatments such as fire-retardant application must align with these design principles.

Finally, WPP combine good thermal properties with **long-term carbon sequestration** within the building material.

ACHIEVEMENT

The used Chemo-Thermomechanical Pulp (CTMP) fibres were selected as raw material for being the **most cost-efficient** commercially available **fibres** that offer suitable mechanical properties. Other additives are a foaming agent that is commonly used in household products such as toothpastes or shampoos and a fire retardant to fulfill the fire safety standards (Euroclass E). The mechanical and thermal **insulation properties** of the panels are **comparable to** commercially available **wood fibre insulation panels** and thus are **very light weight** suitable for easy handling in construction assembly.

✓ Process

- 1- Foaming of fibres and water to 50% air content
- 2- Forming and drying
- 3- Fire retardant treatment

BENEFITS

- Equal insulation performance as existing wood-based products
- Very light weight, no specific training need for assembly
- Made from renewable, wood pulp
- Recycled wood can be utilized as a raw material
- Lowers greenhouse gas emissions and stores CO₂ in building walls
- Easy to be recycled and used in circular economy value chains (if suitable fire retardant is used)

CIRCULARITY

FURTHER R&D

VTT is currently identifying partners for industrial production and additional fine-tuning of properties adapted to an industrial production process.

Ongoing long-term monitoring of the product in the KUBIK experimental building of Tecnalia, Spain, might reveal further optimisation potential.

Next Steps

- Scale up production process with industry partner
- Fine-tuning of properties
- In-use monitoring in KUBIK experimental building

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The project has received a 10M€ grant funding from the *EU Horizon 2020 R&I programme*. It includes 29 partners from 12 countries including 8 leading research and technology organizations, 3 universities, 14 companies and 4 other public and sectoral organizations. The team unites strong expertise in wood construction systems and buildings, innovative materials, architecture, forestry, digitalisation, environmental assessment and rural development. It covers regions in Northern, Central and Southern Europe.

